

Murine Islet Preparation

For islet isolation, 8-week old C57/BL6 mice were injected intraperitoneally with 270 mg/kg ketamine/15 mg/kg xylazine (anesthesia overdose). A cannula was prepared by filling with collagenase solution (CIzyme, Vitacyte, Indianapolis, IN) a syringe fitted with a 27 G needle. After an incision made in the lower abdomen (V cut), the pancreas was exposed, the pancreatic duct was clamped off at its duodenal insertion with a small bulldog clamp and the cannula was inserted into the duct proximal to the liver. Collagenase solution (3 ml/mouse) was injected to fully inflate the pancreas, which was subsequently removed and placed in a 50-ml conical tube for 20-30 min in a 37°C water bath. At the end of the incubation, RPMI 1640 medium with 10% FBS was added (~20 ml) to each tube. The tubes were hand shaken vigorously for 5-10 seconds to break up the tissue and were kept in ice. Samples were washed three times to remove the collagenase by centrifugation at 180xg for 1.5 min. The supernatant was poured off, medium was added (~25 ml) and the samples were vortexed gently. The suspension was filtered through a 400- μ m wire mesh (VWR, Randor, PA). The filtrate containing islets and exocrine tissue was spun at 180xg for 1.5 min and the supernatant was removed. The pellet was resuspended in 10-15 ml Histopaque 1077 (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO) and vortexed until the suspension was homogeneous. After overlaying with 10 ml of RPMI 1640 medium the sample was spun for 20 min at 1750xg with very slow acceleration and no braking at 10°C. Islets were collected from the interface with a 10-ml serological pipette and placed in a 50-ml conical tube. Exocrine tissue was collected from the bottom of the gradient and harvested to 50 ml-conical tubes. After three washes with RPMI 1640 with 10% FBS and centrifugation at 180xg for 1.5 min the islet fraction was transferred to 6-cm sterile culture dishes for islet picking.